

used: oven 220°; I. P.-260°; F. I. D.-270°. Carrier gas nitrogen, 25 ml/min. The GLC apparatus used was an F & M, model 700 of Hewlett and Packard, (U. S. A.)

Due to the paucity of the plant material further investigation could not be undertaken.

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References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, p. 105.
2. AURVEDACHARYA S. K. BHATTACHARYA, (Personal communications).
3. S. S. BHATTACHARYA, P. K. SARKAR, A. K. BARUA and P. CHAKRABARTI, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1970-71, 33-34, 9.
4. S. R. JOHNS, J. A. LAMBERTON, A. A. SIOUMIS and J. A. WUNDERLICH, *Chem. Comm.*, 1968, 290.

Determination of Ascorbic acid with Potassium iodate, Iodine, Potassium bromate and Iodine monochloride using Naphthol blue black, Amaranth and Brilliant Ponceau 5R as indicators

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ERDEY and Bodor⁷ standardised the ascorbic acid against potassium iodate or iodine solutions to the disappearance of the colour caused by iodine. Lorenz, Reynolds and Stevans² used starch as indicator in the titration of iodine. Ballantine³ used starch as indicator in the titration of potassium iodate. Szekers, Sugar and Pop⁴ used starch in the estimation of potassium bromate in the presence of potassium iodide. Cihalik⁵ used starch as indicator in the titration of ascorbic acid with iodine monochloride. But Erdey and Bodor⁷ and Gopala Rao and Narayana Rao⁶ were of the opinion that starch cannot be used as indicator in these titrations since it decreases the reaction rate between ascorbic acid and iodine. Variamine blue is proposed as the indicator in the place of starch by Erdey and Kaplar^{7a} and by Cihalik⁵ in the titrations of ascorbic acid with iodine and potassium iodate and in iodine monochloride respectively. Deshmukh and Bapat³ used carbon tetrachloride in the titration of potassium iodate. Singh, Kashyap and Sahota⁹ used chloroform in the presence of mercuric chloride in the

titration of ascorbic acid with iodine monochloride. Schulek, Kovaes and Rozsa¹⁰ used *p*-ethoxy chrysoidine as indicator with potassium bromate in the presence of potassium bromide. The authors stated that the end point is not so sharp as that of starch-iodide blue colour. In view of these varied concepts regarding the successful use of indicators we tried to use naphthol blue black, amaranth and brilliant ponceau 5R in the standardisation and estimation of ascorbic acid with potassium iodate or iodine solutions. The indicators were also successfully used in the titrations of ascorbic acid with potassium bromate and iodine monochloride solutions.

Experimental

All the reagents used unless otherwise stated were of Analar (B. D. H.) quality. The indicators employed were of 0.2 per cent. aqueous solutions. 0.1*N* iodine¹¹ and iodine monochloride^{1a} solutions were prepared and standardised^{11,1a} against standard solution of arsenic(III) 0.1*N* potassium iodate and potassium bromate (Sarabhai M. Chemicals G.R. Proanalysis grade) were prepared and standardised iodometrically with sodium thiosulphate which in turn standardised with potassium dichromate.

0.1*N* solution of ascorbic acid (Sarabhai M. Chemicals G. R. Proanalysis grade) was prepared by dissolving required amount in one litre in the presence of stabilising agents EDTA and formic acid¹ and standardised against standard solution of potassium iodate¹.

Procedure: An aliquot volume of ascorbic acid is taken in a 150 ml. flask and the required amount of hydrochloric acid is added to give an over all acid concentration of 0.1-2.0*N* for potassium iodate, 0.1-1.0*N* for iodine, 0.2-0.3*N* for potassium bromate and 1-2.5*N* for iodine monochloride titrations. To the mixture about 0.1 ml. of the indicator solution is added and the titration is carried out against the respective oxidant. In the estimation of ascorbic acid with potassium iodate and potassium bromate 2-10 ml. of one per cent. solution of potassium iodide is added before the titration is carried. The colour changes are from blue to green for naphthol blue black and from rose pink to brownish yellow for both amaranth and brilliant ponceau 5R. The colour changes are fairly reversible and the indicator correction is negligible in such titrations.

Reverse titration: Naphthol blue black, amaranth and brilliant ponceau 5R can as well be used as indicators in the titrations of potassium iodate, potassium bromate, iodine and iodine monochloride solutions with ascorbic acid. In the titrations of potassium iodate and potassium bromate 10 per cent. solution of potassium iodide is used to liberate the iodine correspondingly and the liberated iodine is titrated with ascorbic acid.

Chloride, sulphate, nitrate, acetate, borate, tartarate, citrate, phosphate, antimonate, potash alum, manganese(II), zinc(II), barium(II), glucose, sucrose, fructose,

sodium and potassium do not interfere in these titrations. But the green colour of nickel sulphate interferes with the indicator colour change of naphthol blue black while such difficulty does not appear with the colour changes of amaranth and brilliant ponceau 5R. Similarly the pink colour of cobalt chloride interferes with the indicator colour changes of amaranth and brilliant ponceau 5R while it does not interfere in the case of naphthol blue black. Copper(II), arsenic(III), mercury(II), cysteine, thiourea, thioglycolic acid, sulphide, sulphite, thiosulphate interfere at all concentrations.

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References

1. A. BERKA, J. VULTERIN and J. ZYKA, "Newyer Redox Titrants", Pergamon Press, 1965, p. 162.
- 1a. *Ibid.*, p. 56.
2. A. J. LORENZ, R. W. RENOLDS and S. J. W. STEVANS, Symposium on Vitamins, 92 meeting of Amer. Chem. Soc., Pittsburg Pa., 1936.
3. BALLENTINE, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Edn.*, 1941, 13, 89.
4. L. SZEKERES, E. SUGAR and E. POP, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1951, 121, 17.
5. J. CIHALIK, Doctoral thesis, University of Chem. Technology, Prague, 1957.
6. G. GOPALA RAO and V. NARAYANA RAO, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1955, 147, 338.
7. L. ERDEY and E. BODOR, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1952, 24, 418. cf. *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1952/53, 137, 293.
- 7a. L. ERDEY and L. KAPLAR, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1958, 162, 180.
8. G. S. DESHMUKH and M. G. BAPAT, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1955, 145, 254.
9. B. SINGH, G. P. KASHYAP and S. S. SAHOTA, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1958, 162, 357.
10. E. SCHULEK, J. KOVAES and R. ROZSA, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1951, 121, 17.
11. I. M. KOLTHOFF, et. al. Volumetric Analysis, III. Interscience publisher, Inc., New York, 1957, pp. 222, 231.

Identification of Sugars and Organic Acids in Bananas

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THE most conspicuous change in ripening of bananas is the conversion of starch to sugars and changes in flavour. Wali and Hassan¹ reported the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose in bananas. Lulla and Johar² detected sugars in south Indian bananas. Wyman and Palmer³ identified and malic, citric and oxalic acids

in ripe Gros Michel banana. The present study reports the identification of sugars and organic acids by chromatography in bananas viz. Basrai, Harichal, Lalkel (variety of *Musa cavendishii*), Rajeli, Safed velchi (variety of *Musa paradisiaca*) cultivated around the coast of Bombay, Maharashtra State. The purpose of the present communication is to report the various sugars and organic acids detected on paper chromatogram in the indigenous varieties of ripen bananas.

Experimental

Sugars : 20 g. of banana pulp were homogenised with 70% alcohol for the extraction of sugars. The alcoholic slurry was strained through a cheese cloth and centrifuged. The clear extracts were made alcohol free on a water bath and made upto a known volume. The presence of sugars in banana pulp extract solvent-5 *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 5) was used as developer and aniline hydrogen phthalate⁶ as spraying reagent and location of the various sugar spots was identified.

Organic acids : 50 g. of banana pulp were extracted in cold with two volumes of 70% alcohol. The supernatants were concentrated and made upto a known volume. The extracts were directly passed through an anion exchange column of Dowex-1 (200-400 mesh) in the formate form to absorb all the organic acids. The organic acids were fractionally displaced from the column with 4 *N* formic acid. The elutes containing organic acids were freed of formic acid by evaporating to dryness under reduced pressure at 40°. The dried sample was redissolved in 0.8 ml of 5 *N* sulphuric acid and slurried with one gram of silica gel. This slurry was then transferred to a silica gel column and the acids were separated and identified as outlined by Marvel and Rands⁷.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that paper chromatographic separation of sugars in bananas showed the presence of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose. Maki et. al⁸ reported the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose in ripe Taiwan bananas. Poland et al⁹ identified glucose, fructose, sucrose as the major sugars in banana pulp. Lulla and Johar² analysed the sugars in different species of bananas. The present findings are in accordance with those reported by Lulla and Johar and confirmed. It was also found that among organic acids, citric and malic acids were detected in all varieties of bananas studied in the present investigation. Palmer and Wyman³ reported the presence of citric, malic and oxalic acids in high concentration. Edward Ross et al¹⁰ identified small quantities of phosphoric acid in addition to citric and malic acid in chinese banana. Lulla and Johar¹¹ determined organic acids and reported that citric and malic acids were present. In the present findings malic acid was found to be predominant among the samples studied.

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